

PUSH-IT

Piloting Underground Seasonal Heat Storage In geothermal reservoirs

A cross-national and local survey of underground thermal energy storage perceptions: survey instrument

Funded by
the European Union

Grant agreement number	101096566		
Project title	Piloting Underground Storage of Heat In geoThermal reservoirs		
Project acronym	PUSH-IT		
Start date	01-01-2023	DURATION	48 months
End date	31-12-2026		
Work Package No. and Title	WP2 Public engagement, societal benefit and risks		
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List of Abbreviations

EU	European Union
JLP	Johnson Lubbock Partners
km	Kilometers
N	Total survey sample size
n	Subgroup sample size
PUSH-IT	Piloting Underground Storage of Heat In geoThermal reservoirs
UTES	Underground Thermal Energy Storage

1. Introduction

Underground Thermal Energy Storage (UTES) offers the potential to manage seasonal demand for heat, thereby reducing reliance on fossil fuels. The Horizon EU project PUSH-IT (Piloting Underground Storage of Heat In geoThermal reservoirs) is testing three ways to store heat up to 90°C, in mines, boreholes and aquifers. The project also explores governance, policies, business models, and societal engagement.

We worked with market research agency Johnson Lubbock Partners (JLP) to manage and distribute a 15-minute online questionnaire (N=5,800) to nationally representative samples (n=1,000) across each of four countries (Germany, the Netherlands, the Czech Republic, and the United Kingdom) and locally representative samples (n=300) in each of six communities within 20 km of pilot sites (Figure 1).

The questionnaire examined awareness of and attitudes towards UTES, trust in operators, awareness of engagement practices, and the impacts of engagement on understanding and support. This research note shares the survey instrument we used to gather this data.

Figure 1: Survey distribution

2. Survey instrument

The following wording was used for the UK national and Cornwall local questionnaires. Note, **HIGHLIGHTED** question titles and [statements in brackets] were not shown to respondents. Categories for EDUCATION, REGION and POLITIC were tailored for each country.

Energy questionnaire

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Welcome. This questionnaire asks for your thoughts and opinions about energy. **You do not need to have any specific knowledge or experience to take part**, and you will be provided with more information during the questionnaire.

The questionnaire is being carried out by researchers at the University of Exeter and Anglia Ruskin University in the UK, as part of a project called PUSH-IT, funded by the European Union.

The questionnaire will take around **15 minutes**. All views are important to us, so please answer all questions as best you can. We value your time and hope you will enjoy taking part.

All questions are **optional**, and the questionnaire is **anonymous**: your answers cannot be traced back to you, and you will not be identified in any reported results.

The information you provide will be used for research and statistical purposes, and will be processed in accordance with the latest **Data Protection** regulations. All data will be stored on password protected, secure servers. Upon completion of the analysis and publication process, fully anonymized survey data will be made freely accessible on [Zenodo](#) (a repository where researchers share their data).

This questionnaire has been approved by Anglia Ruskin University research ethics committee. Questions and comments can be addressed to Dr Merryn Thomas: m.j.thomas@exeter.ac.uk.

The data controller for this project is JL Partners (research partner, <https://jlparters.co.uk/privacy-notice>). The data processors are Cint (sample provider, <https://www.cint.com/privacy-policy/>), Number Cruncher Analytics (sample provider, <https://www.ncpolitics.uk/privacy-policy/>), Alchemer (survey tool provider, <https://www.alchemer.com/privacy/>), Anglia Ruskin University (researchers, <https://aru.ac.uk/privacy-and-cookies/research-participants>) and the University of Exeter (researchers, <https://www.exeter.ac.uk/about/oursite/privacy/research/#a6>).

Before you start, **please read the statements**:

- I am over 18 years old, and I understand the information above.
- I understand that taking part in this questionnaire is entirely voluntary.
- The answers that I give will be anonymous.
- There is no way that anyone will be able to link my answers back to me.
- My answers may be used anonymously in project outputs (e.g., journal articles, reports).
- If I decide I do not want to participate, I can close the questionnaire and my responses will be deleted.
- Once I press submit, it is not possible for me to withdraw my answers.

Yes, I consent

No, I do not consent [TERMINATE]

The first questions are to make sure we ask a broad range of people.

1. **AGE** What is your age? ____
 - Prefer not to say

2. **GENDER** Are you- ?
 - Female
 - Male
 - Non-binary
 - Other/prefer to self-describe _____
 - Prefer not to say

3. **EDUCATION** What is the highest level of education you have completed? Please select one.
Please scroll to view all options.
 - No formal schooling
 - Primary school
 - Secondary school (e.g. O-Level, GCSE)
 - Sixth form / College (e.g., A-Levels, AS Levels, NVQ)
 - HNC, HND, BTEC Level 4 or equivalent
 - Foundation Degree or equivalent
 - Degree or equivalent (e.g., Bachelor's Degree)
 - Post-graduate degree (e.g., Masters, PhD)
 - Prefer not to say

4. **REGION** [national survey only] Where do you live? [List regions from quota] [If in a region containing a study site, proceed to 5a. If not, proceed to 6b (this is the 'national distant' sample)]. *Please scroll to view all options.*
 - East of England
 - East Midlands
 - London
 - North East
 - North West
 - South East
 - South West
 - West Midlands
 - Yorkshire and the Humber
 - Scotland

- Wales
- Northern Ireland

5. **5a PROXIMITY** [national survey only]

We are interested in whether views differ with distance from energy projects. The map shows the location of an energy project in **circle 'a'** [a, b, c, for Germany] which we will return to later in the questionnaire. Do you live within or near the circle ['circles' for Germany map]? If you're not sure, please give your best guess (pinch or use Ctrl +/- to zoom).

- 1 Yes, I live in or near circle 'a'
- 2 [circle b, Germany only]
- 3 [circle c, Germany only]
- 4 No, I do not live in or near the circle
- 5 Don't know

[if answer 4 or 5, this is the 'national distant' sample. If answer 1,2,3, show 5b]:

5b: PROXIMITY [national respondents answering yes (1-3) to 5a only: insert relevant local map with circles and labels]

Thank you. We have labelled the map with a little more detail. Do you live in any of these areas? If you're not sure, please give your best guess (pinch or use Ctrl +/- to zoom).

1. a [0-2km] [this is the 'proximate national' sample]
2. b [2-5km] [this is the 'proximate national' sample]
3. c [5-10km] [this is the 'proximate national' sample]
4. d [10-20km] [this is the 'proximate national' sample]
5. e [Outside the 20km radius] [this is the 'distant national' sample]
6. None of these [this is the 'distant national' sample]

5c PROXIMITY [all local survey respondents]

We are interested in whether views differ with distance from energy projects. The map shows the location of an energy project in **circle 'a'**, which we will return to later in the questionnaire. Which area do you live in? If you do not live anywhere on the map, please select the area you are currently visiting. If you're not sure, please give your best guess (pinch or use Ctrl +/- to zoom).

1. a [0-2km] [this is the local sample]
2. b [2-5km] [this is the local sample]
3. c [5-10km] [this is the local sample]
4. d [10-20km] [this is the local sample]
5. e [Outside the 20km radius] [TERMINATE]
6. None of these [TERMINATE]

6. **RESIDENT 6a** ['LOCAL sample only]

What best describes your relationship with the area shown on the map?

1. I visit here but live elsewhere
2. I work or study here but live elsewhere
3. I have a home here but also live elsewhere
4. I live here and have done for 0-2 years
5. I live here and have done for 3-9 years
6. I live here and have done for 10-20 years
7. I live here and have done for over 20 years

RESIDENT 6b ['NATIONAL DISTANT and NATIONAL PROXIMATE samples]

For how long have you lived in your local area? This could be the city, district, town, or village that you live in

4. 0-2 years
5. 3-9 years
6. 10-20 years
7. over 20 years

7. **ATTACHMENT**

[National DISTANT and NATIONAL PROXIMATE respondents and any respondents who answered 6.4-6.7]: Please answer this question for **your local area**. This could be the city, district, town, or village that you live in. To what extent do you agree or disagree that:

[*Visiting* respondents (any respondents who answered 1-3 in Q6a)]: Please answer this question for **the local area that you are visiting, staying or working in (on the map)**. This could be the city, district, town, or village that you are in. To what extent do you agree or disagree that:

[randomize statements]	Strongly agree 	Don't know				
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This is my favourite place						
I feel like I don't belong in this area						
This place says a lot about who I am						
This is the best place for what I like to do						
No other place can compare to this place						
Nature is an important part of this place						
The community is an important part of this place						
What is under the ground (below the earth's surface) is an important part of this place						

8. Q8 **EXPERIENCE** Have you had any of the following experiences of the underground (below the earth's surface)? Experiences could be local or elsewhere. They could be **direct** experiences (e.g., a caving trip you did) or **through your family or community** (e.g., having a grandparent who worked in mining, or having a geothermal power plant in your community). Please tick all that apply [randomised, apart from 'other' and 'no experience']. *Please scroll to view all options.*

Visiting the underground (e.g., caving, tourism)
Mining or drilling (e.g., for coal, gas, metals, minerals)
Using the earth's heat to produce energy (geothermal energy)
Using shallow underground systems to heat and cool buildings (ground source heat pumps)
Storing heat underground to use later (underground thermal energy storage)
Communal heating through pipes (district heating)
Research (e.g., science experiments or testing new technologies underground)
Underground radiation (e.g., radon exposure, nuclear waste storage)
Other (please state) _____
I have had no experience of the underground

- Q8b **EXP_POSNEG** Please indicate whether each experience was generally positive, negative or neither. [Filtered to only show the activities selected in Q8, in the same order as 8]

	Very positive experience 	Don't know				
Visiting the underground (e.g., caving, tourism)						
Mining or drilling (e.g., for coal, gas, metals, minerals)						
Using heat from underground (geothermal energy)						
Using shallow underground systems to heat and cool buildings (ground source heat pumps)						
Storing heat underground to use later (underground thermal energy storage)						
Communal heating through pipes (district heating)						
Research (e.g., science experiments or testing new technologies underground)						
Underground radiation (e.g., radon exposure, nuclear waste storage)						
Other (please state) _____						

The rest of this questionnaire concerns an energy technology known as underground thermal energy storage, also known as underground heat storage. You do not need to have any prior knowledge or experience of the topic, and we will provide more information as you go through the questionnaire.

- 9. **TOP_MIND** Please tell us anything that comes to mind when you see the phrase 'underground thermal energy (heat) storage'. All views are important to us, so **please write as much as you can** and do not worry about whether you are 'right' or 'wrong' - this question is about what immediately comes to mind, not about your level of knowledge.

10. **FAMILIAR** Which of the following best describes your familiarity with underground thermal energy (heat) storage?

- I have never heard of it before today
- I have heard of it, but don't know anything about it
- I have a basic understanding
- I have a moderate understanding
- I have an in-depth understanding

Underground thermal energy (heat) storage is a technology that stores energy as heat beneath the earth's surface. Heat from power plants, factories, and renewable energy sources (e.g., solar, geothermal) can be collected in summer.

The heat is then stored underground until it is needed in winter, for example, to supply local or district heat networks. This can help reduce the use of fossil fuels such as coal, oil, and gas.

The hotter the temperature, the more energy stored. Scientists are testing three ways to store heat up to 90°C, as shown in the diagrams.

Underground thermal energy (heat) storage in aquifers, boreholes and disused mines. Not to scale.

Throughout the rest of the questionnaire, we will refer to underground thermal energy storage as 'underground heat storage'.

The **Piloting Underground Storage of Heat in Geothermal Reservoirs (PUSH-IT)** project is testing underground heat storage up to 90°C at sites in the UK, Netherlands, Czech Republic, and Germany. One site is at United Downs, Cornwall, shown on the map (pinch or use Ctrl +/- to zoom).

[UK national distant sample]

United Downs, Cornwall (Circle 'A')

[Cornwall local sample and UK national proximate sample]:

United Downs, Cornwall (Circle 'a')

11. **EMOTION** When thinking about underground heat storage development within circle 'a' on the map, to what extent do you feel...

	Very much	Moderately	A little	Not at all	Don't know
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Surprised					
Hopeful					
Proud					
Happy					
Sad					
Worried					
Exploited					
Threatened					
Indifferent					

12. **ADVANTAGE** In your opinion, what could be **the main advantages** of underground heat storage in disused mines, aquifers and/or boreholes? Please think about who or what could be positively impacted. All views are important to us so **please write as much as you can** in the box and do not worry whether you are ‘right’ or ‘wrong’ - we are interested in your thoughts rather than your level of knowledge.

13. **DISADV** In your opinion, what could be **the main disadvantages** of underground heat storage in disused mines, aquifers and/or boreholes? Please think about who or what could be negatively impacted.

14. **SUPPORT** Knowing what you know, to what extent would you support or oppose the development of underground heat storage in the following areas?

	Strongly support 	Don't know				
In your local area (e.g., your city, district, village)						
In your region or county						
In your country						

15. **BEN_IMPO** Regardless of how likely you think they are to happen, which potential advantages from underground heat storage are **most important** to you, in the areas where it is developed? Please **select up to three**. [randomise order]
Please scroll to view all options.

- Reduced household energy costs
- Lower greenhouse gas emissions, contributing to a more sustainable local environment
- Less air pollution (e.g., sulphur dioxide, nitrogen oxides) from burning fossil fuels
- More education and engagement activities for local people
- Greater community ownership of energy resources
- More community involvement in decision-making
- More local job opportunities and business for local companies
- New networks of communal heating through pipes (district heating)
- Increased funding for community projects and local infrastructure improvements
- Other (please specify) _____
- None

16. **ATTENTION** You are around halfway through the questionnaire. Please select the relevant option:

- I have just started the questionnaire [TERMINATE]
- I am around halfway through the questionnaire
- Don't know [TERMINATE]

17. **AWARE** Before taking part in this questionnaire, were you aware of any underground heat storage projects? This includes past, present and planned projects. Note, this is about **storing** heat underground, not generating heat underground.

- Yes
- No
- Don't know

[IF 'yes', show Q18 – Q21. Otherwise go to Q22]

18. **PROJECT** Please tell us a few words about the underground heat storage project(s) you were aware of before taking part in this questionnaire. For example, the project's name or what it involved. If you do not know or cannot remember, this is OK - please proceed to the next question.

19. **ACTIVITY** Not including this questionnaire, have you taken part in any activities **related with underground heat storage**, in your local area or elsewhere? Please tick all that apply.

[randomised]

Please scroll to view all options.

Activity	
Questionnaire (not including this one)	
Interview by researcher or journalist	
Focus group or workshop to gather community views	
Formal hearing or town hall meeting to discuss and consult	
Educational activities or scientific research	
Webinar, seminar, or conference	
Project site visit	
Visit to an exhibition or stand at an event	
Informal event (e.g., BBQ, coffee morning)	
Read or listened to newspaper, radio, TV	
Viewed online report, blog, email update, social media	
Other (please state) _____	
I have not participated in any activities related with underground heat storage	

20. **ACT_UND** For each of the activities you took part in, how did it affect your **understanding of underground heat storage**? [Filtered to only show the activities selected in Q19, in the same order]

Activity	Greatly increased my understanding 	Don't know				
Questionnaire (not including this one)						
Interview by researcher or journalist						
Focus group or workshop to gather community views						
Formal hearing or town hall meeting to discuss and consult						
Educational activities or scientific research						

Webinar, seminar, or conference							
Project site visit							
Visit to an exhibition or stand at an event							
Informal event (e.g., BBQ, coffee morning)							
Read or listened to newspaper, radio, TV							
Viewed online report, blog, email update, social media							
Other (please state) _____							

21. **ACT_SUP** For each of the activities you took part in, how did it affect your level of support for or opposition to underground heat storage? [Filtered to only show the activities selected in Q19, in the same order]

Activity	Greatly increased my level of support 	Don't know				
Questionnaire (not including this one)						
Interview by researcher or journalist						
Focus group or workshop to gather community views						
Formal hearing or town hall meeting to discuss and consult						
Educational activities or scientific research						
Webinar, seminar, or conference						
Project site visit						
Visit to an exhibition or stand at an event						
Informal event (e.g., BBQ, coffee morning)						

Read or listened to newspaper, radio, TV							
Viewed online report, blog, email update, social media							
Other (please state) _____							

22. **TRUST** How much would you trust each of the following to competently carry out their role in relation to underground heat storage **in your local area**? [randomise]

	Strongly trust 	Don't know or not applicable				
Local council (e.g., city, county)						
Regional government						
National government						
Environmental regulator (Environment Agency, Natural Resources Wales, Scottish Environment Protection Agency, Northern Ireland Environment Agency)						
Mining or water authorities						
National or international non-governmental organisation (NGO)						
Independent engineering or environmental consulting firm						
Community energy group (e.g., a cooperative)						
Local company						
National or international company						
University						

23. **DECISION** We are interested in your thoughts about **how decisions should be made about underground heat storage projects**. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements? [randomise order]

[randomize statements]	Strongly agree 	Don't know				

People living near projects should receive more advantages from these projects than people living far away						
The unique character of local areas (e.g., landscape, culture) should be prioritised above other considerations in planning decisions						
Local people should be informed as early as possible about projects						
Informing local people early on in development could create unnecessary anxiety						
Decisions should be made only by qualified experts						
Where possible, new projects should happen mainly in areas where energy projects (e.g. wind turbines, coal mines) have not happened before						
Decisions about projects should prioritise future generations						

24. **DEMOS** We are interested in your thoughts about **the role of pilot and demonstration projects** in developing new energy technologies like underground heat storage. To what extent do you agree or disagree with the following statements? [randomise order]

[randomize statements]	Strongly agree	Moderately agree 	Strongly disagree	Don't know		
------------------------	----------------	---	----------------------------	--	-------------------	------------

Scientists should only test new energy technologies that are very likely to succeed						
Taking some environmental risks is necessary to develop new energy technologies						
Scientists should only test new energy technologies that have public support						
Testing new energy technologies should be supported with public money						

25. **CC_WORRY** How worried, if at all, are you about climate change?

- Not at all worried
- Not very worried
- Fairly worried
- Very worried
- Extremely worried
- Don't know

26. **CC_SCEPT** Thinking about the current causes of climate change, which, if any, of the following best describes your opinion? *Please scroll to view all options.*

- Climate change is entirely caused by natural processes (e.g., solar activity, volcanoes)
- Climate change is mainly caused by natural processes (e.g., solar activity, volcanoes)
- Climate change is caused about equally by natural processes and human activity
- Climate change is mainly caused by human activity (e.g., burning fossil fuels)
- Climate change is entirely caused by human activity (e.g., burning fossil fuels)
- There is no such thing as climate change
- Don't know

27. **QUESTIONS** Imagine you could ask an expert anything about underground heat storage. What would you ask? Once the survey has closed, we will provide answers to frequently asked questions (information at the end of the survey).
-

28. **POLITIC** Which political party do you most identify with?

- Conservative
- Labour
- Liberal Democrat
- Reform UK
- Green
- Scottish National Party
- Plaid Cymru
- Other (please specify)
- I do not identify with any party
- Prefer not to say

29. **UNDERREP** Do you personally identify as belonging to a group that is historically or currently underrepresented in certain areas of society, such as gender, cultural background, disability, or socioeconomic status?

- Yes
- No
- Don't know
- Prefer not to say

Thank you for taking part in our questionnaire. **Please press Submit**

Thank you.

This research is part of a project called PUSH-IT (Piloting Underground Storage of Heat In geoThermal reservoirs), which aims to overcome the seasonal mismatch between heat demand and heat generation from sustainable sources using underground heat storage. As well as developing technologies, the project explores societal engagement, governance, policies, and business models.

This questionnaire aims to a) gauge public understanding and attitudes toward underground heat storage, b) measure trust in operators, c) track effectiveness of engagement efforts, and d) compare responses between sites, and between local and national contexts.

More information about the project and each site can be found here: <https://www.push-it-thermalstorage.eu/>. **Answers to common questions** will be posted on the PUSH-IT website when we have analysed responses to the survey.

Further questions and comments can be addressed to Dr Merryn Thomas: m.j.thomas@exeter.ac.uk.

[Show only to local and proximate national respondents:]

If you would like to be recontacted **about opportunities to take part in further research** about underground heat storage (e.g., a focus group), please click here: [link]

This will take you to a separate website, administered by the University of Exeter and Anglia Ruskin University, where you can provide your contact information. Participation is entirely voluntary.

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3. Acknowledgements

We would like to thank all our respondents and pilot participants for taking part in this research. We also sincerely thank members of the PUSH-IT consortium for their assistance with translation and advising on survey text and diagrams, especially Veronika Slavíková, Katrin Kieling, Elke Mugova, Markus Schedel, Tom Olver, Jane Charman, Serge Santoo, Martin Bloemendal, Phil Vardon, Jan Brabec, Florian Hahn, Andres Gonzalez Quiros, Lukas Seib, Hung Pham, Danitsja van Heusden-van Winden, Stefan Klein, and Annick Loschetter. We would also like to thank Christina Demski, Kat Steentjes and Anna Pellizzone for their comments on early versions of the survey. Thanks also to Jonathan Roorda at Videomatic for working with us on the diagrams, and the team at JPL – especially Joe Alder.